

the surface membrane or as Ge accumulation in the surface membrane.

The As suspension showed about 40% destruction of the spherical mitochondrion. That can be explained by the As mechanism of arsenolysis of macroergical compounds, leading to mitochondria membrane degradation. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter invites contributions of concise summaries of significant current rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to no more than 2 pages typed double-spaced, accompanied by no more than 2 figures, tables, or photographs. Contributions are reviewed by appropriate IRRI scientists and those accepted are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors are identified by name and research organization. See inside front cover for more information about submissions.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Grain quality of new Pakistani rice lines

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Four promising lines—AS688, IR25588-7-3-1, IR28128-45-2, and PND160-2-1—from the 1985 Irrigated Rice Yield Nursery-Very Early yielded higher than local varieties grown in Mansehra and Muzaffarabad. The lines were further tested 1986-87 in microplot trials.

On the basis of total milling recovery, physical dimensions, chemical properties, and cooking and eating quality, AS688 resembled JP5, IR28128-45-2 resembled DR83, and PND160-2-1 resembled KS282 (see table).

The new lines are likely to be acceptable to local millers and consumers. □

Grain characteristics of 4 early-maturing rice lines and 3 local commercial varieties.^a Pakistan, 1985-87.

Entry	Total recovery (%)	Head rice (%)	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Length-to-breadth ratio	Size/shape ^b	Grain thickness (mm)	Quality index ($\frac{L}{B \times T}$)
<i>Lines</i>								
AS688	67.8	42.4	5.3	2.6	2.0	S/B	2.0	1.0
IR25588-7-3-1	69.0	63.8	6.3	2.1	3.0	M/M	1.8	1.7
IR28128-45-2	66.2	59.8	6.6	1.9	3.5	L/S	1.6	2.2
PND160-2-1	64.0	47.0	6.6	1.7	3.9	L/S	1.6	2.4
<i>Local varieties</i>								
DR83	66.8	54.4	6.8	2.0	3.4	L/S	1.9	1.8
JP5	72.8	55.2	4.9	2.8	1.8	S/B	2.3	0.8
KS282	69.6	58.3	7.0	2.0	3.5	L/S	1.8	2.0
	Chalky grain (%)	Elongation ratio	Cooked grain appearance ^c		Protein (N × 5.95) % (db)	Amylose (% basis)	Alkali spreading value	Gelatinization temperature ^d (alkali basis)
<i>Lines</i>								
AS688	10	1.8	S		8.3	19	6.4	L
IR25588-7-3-1	6	1.5	S/S		7.9	23	5.9	I
IR28128-45-2	4	1.4	SE		8.0	25	7.0	L
PND160-2-1	5	1.8	W/SE		8.3	27	7.0	L
<i>Local varieties</i>								
DR83	8	1.6	SE		8.5	22	5.2	I
JP5	4	1.7	S		8.6	18	6.3	L
KS282	Nil	2.0	SE		8.3	28	7.0	L

^aAv of 3 replications. ^bS/B = short/bold, M/M = medium/medium, L/S = long/slender. ^cS = sticky, S/S = slightly sticky, SE = separated, W/SE = well separated. ^dL = low, I = intermediate.

Disease resistance

Scoring systems for evaluating rice varietal resistance to bacterial blight (BB): lesion size by growth stage

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Host plant resistance to pathogens can be measured using different parameters—latent period, pathogen

sporulation and growth in host tissues. In most cases, disease symptoms (lesion area, length, etc.) are scored according to an indexing scale based on the assumption that the lesion reflects pathogen growth in the host quantitatively, as a response of the host to infection.

We measured lesion development at different growth stages on 22 rice cultivars grown in pots in the greenhouse and infected with BB isolate PXO61 of race 1.

Planting was staggered to synchronize inoculation at different growth stages.

Total leaf area was measured using a leaf area meter at 11, 14, and 17 d after inoculation. Lesions were cut from individual leaves, the lesion area measured, and percentage infected leaf area calculated.

The cultivars were classified into three groups. Group 1 (including TN1) was highly susceptible at 20 d after sowing (DAS), but the lesion areas gradually decreased from 30 to 50 DAS and became constant from 50 to 80 DAS (see table). In group 2, lesion area decreased from 20 to 40 DAS but the plants remained susceptible. Lesions

BB lesion development at 11, 14, and 17 d after inoculation on rice cultivars infected with isolate PXO61 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* race 1 at different growth stages. IRRI, 1987.

Plant age (DAS)	Lesion area ^a (%)		
	Group 1 ^b	Group 2 ^c	Group 3 ^d
	<i>11 DAI</i>		
20	79.7– 87.7 a	53.6–55.5 a	0.8– 4.0 a
30	63.8– 69.4 b	33.9–50.4 a	0.7– 3.0 a
40	27.7– 39.8 c	21.4–18.4 b	0.6– 0.9 a
50	12.6– 25.6 cd	8.3– 7.3 b	0.5– 0.6 a
60	10.8– 21.1 cd	6.8– 6.0 b	0.4– 0.5 a
70	8.2– 16.8 d	4.0– 5.0 b	0.4– 0.6 a
80	5.1– 18.2 d	1.0– 3.4 b	1.2–170 a
	<i>14 DAI</i>		
20	96.3– 98.7 a	72.2–85.6 a	1.5– 7.5 a
30	90.1– 92.3 a	47.6–79.3 a	1.0– 6.2 a
40	50.8– 62.7 b	28.4–33.9 b	0.9– 2.1 a
50	27.5– 41.6 bc	12.1–13.3 bc	0.7– 1.6 a
60	20.6– 37.8 c	9.5–11.0 c	0.7– 1.5 a
70	16.5– 30.7 c	6.8– 9.3 c	0.8– 1.4 a
80	11.3– 31.5 c	2.1– 6.4 c	1.9– 3.0 a
	<i>17 DAI</i>		
20	99.1–100 a	82.3–95.5 a	2.5– 12.2 a
30	97.9– 98.1 a	59.1–92.9 a	2.2– 9.8 a
40	90.9– 79.8 ab	36.2–51.2 b	1.3– 3.1 a
50	42.7– 58.0 bc	15.5–20.4 c	1.0– 2.3 a
60	29.7– 50.7 c	12.1–14.8 c	1.0– 2.4 a
70	26.3– 44.1 c	9.4–13.7 c	1.2– 2.3 a
80	19.2– 47.1 c	4.2–11.1 c	2.5– 3.2 a

^aIn a column within an inoculation date, values followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level. ^bTN1, IR24, RP4-2, IR8, Yolle, M23, IR9101, MTU19. ^cZenith, Pae Moku, Banda Merah, Ase Pute Rone, Gankkyi, Pasle Angga, Kauk Hayin, Pyi Daw Aye. ^dKetan Ireng, Warangal Culture 1263, Sankurcha, IR1545, DV85, Makhmal Mehi.

decreased abruptly at 50 DAS, and were less than 5% at 80 DAS. In group 3, lesion area did not exceed 10% even at

20 DAS (see figure).

These results show that even in a susceptible variety, lesion development

Lesion development in 3 rice cultivars differing in resistance to BB and infected with PXO61 of race 1 at different growth stages. IRRI, 1988.

decreases with plant age. Maximum lesion percentage in a susceptible variety such as TN1, IR8, or IR24 seldom reaches more than 50% of leaf area. This suggests that scoring disease by plant age requires different observation periods. Lesion area in most of the cultivars increased when the plants were younger and decreased as the plants became older. □

Resistance of rice genotypes to bacterial blight (BB)

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During 1987, we screened 50 entries for BB resistance under field conditions at Fuyang Experiment Station. Entries were transplanted in 2 rows of 12 hills each at 20- × 20-cm spacing. BB-infected Guang Lu Ai 4 and local susceptible check Yuan Feng Zao were transplanted in 1 row between each entry and around the test plot.

Soil was sandy loam with medium fertility. The trial plot was fertilized with 75-37.5-25 kg NPK/ ha. Entries were inoculated from maximum tillering to booting with BB suspension of local predominant isolates collected and

Table 1. Resistance of rice cultivars to 3 isolates of BB 21 d after inoculation. CNRI, China, 1987.

Variety, line	Reaction ^a to isolate			Origin
	CN-X12	CN-X1	CN-X3	
IR20	1	1	1	IRRI
BR285-5-6-6-2	3	3	1	Bangladesh
BR319-1-HR28	3	3	3	Bangladesh
B4075D-PN-13-1	1	1	1	Indonesia
C731067	5	5	3	Taiwan, China
DV85	5	5	3	Bangladesh
IR29295-70-1-1-1-3-1	3	3	3	IRRI
IR33355-39-1-1-3	3	3	3	IRRI
Kalimekri 77-5	3	3	3	Bangladesh
Kogyoko	5	5	3	Japan
RP2151-173-1-8	1	1	1	India
RP2151-21-22	3	0	0	India
RP2151-40-1	3	1	1	India
RTN90-4	3	3	3	India
UPR79-80	5	5	3	India

^aBB evaluated by *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

isolated from naturally infected leaves, adjusted to a concentration of 6 × 10⁸ cells/ml by leaf tip clipping method.

Of 50 entries screened, 15 were

resistant to BB and 27 were moderately resistant (Table 1). BR285-5-6-6-2, B4075D-PN-13-1, RTN904, RP2151-173-1-8, RP2151-21-22, and RP2151-40-